

ISic0505

I.Sicily inscription 0505

Language

Latin

Type

votive

Material

mosaic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Salvis Plotino et
2. Rufae Logus serv(us)
3. act(or) port(us) Lilybit[a]ni
4. hoc sacrarium
5. ex voto exornavit

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491731

EDCS 22000811

Bibliography

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